

The Extent of Influence of Famous Composers on a Work of Another

Milana Pak ✉

Tashkent International School, Uzbekistan

Abstract

This study examines the extent to which John Williams, Hans Zimmer, and Ennio Morricone's compositions influence Ludwig Göransson's main theme for *The Mandalorian*. The study emphasizes the blending of traditions in Göransson's experimental approach to scoring by examining thematic motifs, instrumentation, and compositional techniques. A complex blending of influences is revealed by secondary analyses of Williams, Zimmer, and Morricone as well as primary sources, such as the official orchestral score and recording of *The Mandalorian*. Göransson combines Morricone's expressive use of unusual instrumentation and rhythmic motifs, Zimmer's romantic minimalism and hybrid orchestration, and Williams' harmonic sophistication and leitmotifs. This synthesis gives *The Mandalorian* a unique auditory identity while producing a distinctive soundscape that is consistent with the Star Wars universe.

Keywords: *modern composers, soundtrack, musical traditions, compositional styles.*

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Introduction

A film's soundtrack or score is one of its most important components since it leads the audience through every scene. The use of music varies depending on the genre. For example, in a slice-of-life art film, the absence of music mimics the atmosphere of reality. On the other hand, in a big-budget adventure or sci-fi film, epic orchestral arrangements add to the grandeur of the picture (Hadusek, 2022). When silent movies first came out, real orchestras and musicians would play music to go along with the action on the screen. Since then, movie soundtracks have evolved to become more intricate and dynamic, better reflecting the action in each scene. At times, it just functions as subtle background music, blending in with the conversation without drawing attention to itself. At other moments, it screams from the speakers, adding poignancy to a crucial scene in a story plot. A captivating theme song at the beginning of a movie is the best method to capture the attention of the audience. It will establish a tone and atmosphere, grabbing the audience's attention before a single character appears on the screen. That was the case for the TV show "*The Mandalorian*" in 2019. It is centered on the planet Mandalore, following a lone bounty hunter to "the outer reaches of the galaxy far from the authority of the New Republic" (Pometsey, 2020). As the plot develops, the viewers get more drawn in and the music accompanying the show gets more intense.

Even though the *Mandalorian* theme written by Swedish composer Ludwig Göransson is completely original, it still has a Star Wars feel to it, leaning into Wild West harmonies that promise both danger and adventure (Travis, 2023) "Ludwig's music has given '*The Mandalorian*' its own identity, apart from, yet related to, 'Star Wars,'" says producer Favreau (Burlingame). Therefore, I will evaluate *to what extent the film score "The Mandalorian" by Ludwig Göransson is influenced by composers like John Williams, Ennio Morricone, and Hans Zimmer in terms of compositional techniques and thematic motifs* to explore the significance of musical traditions getting passed on and reinterpreted through time, as well as, to understand the creative process

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behind the workings of “The Mandalorian” film scores and comprehend the combination of different inspirations to give the show its distinct sound.

Methodology

First, I will conduct an in-depth analysis and listen to Gorranson’s film score “The Mandalorian”, paying attention to the music instrumentation, overall sound design, melody, harmony, structure, and rhythm. Second, a thorough analysis of compositions by Hans Zimmer, Ennio Morricone, and John Williams to find similarities and patterns in compositional styles, thematic preferences and technical methods using their musical scores, recordings, and interviews.

The primary sources used are the official orchestral musical score of the main theme from “The Mandalorian” as well as its audio. Additionally, videos and interviews with Gorranson comment on the process of creating the music, inspirations, and goals for the music. Secondary sources used are books and articles that provide information on a broader scale and the larger field of music. Furthermore, musical scores analyze individual styles and contributions of Hans Zimmer, Ennio Morricone, and John Williams which will make it easier to find elements or methods that Goransson has used in his score.

As for challenges, during the research, the difficulty was finding in-depth interviews and analyses that focused on Hans Zimmer, John Williams and Ennio Morricone’s impact on Gorransson’s score. While Gorransson’s creative process was discussed and interviews, it took close inspection in musical analysis to uncover direct influences.

Analysis

Hans Zimmer

The term “romantic minimalism” is often employed to describe Hans Zimmer’s compositional style. Zimmer writes music by creating a straightforward, minimalistic romantic melody, which can then be developed or combined with other musical textures like instrumentation lines and patterns (Pratt, 2009). Zimmer uses a minimalist framework in “Time,” which is marked by recurring themes and gradual growth. This approach is consistent with minimalist principles, which tension repetition and simplicity to produce a hypnotic effect (Obendorf, 2009; Saariaho, 1987). These melodic riffs serve the same function as a leitmotif, which is a melodic riff associated with a particular character or circumstance (Smith). He often synchronizes the loudness of real and virtual instruments with the action. Even though an orchestra has 4 horns, Zimmer will add up to 16 if he feels the movie requires it. The same goes for percussion where he would assign 10 percussionists to the toms instead of the usual 2 or 5, and when he needs a dark timbre, he will hire 20 cellists instead of the usual 8. To create large tonal and rhythmic clusters, Zimmer focuses on choirs, strings, brass, percussion, and synths, rather than woodwind instruments. These soundscapes could also feature guitars or other unusual instruments, depending on the movie. While trombones are often used to add larger-than-life accents to compositions, usually in the form of staccatos and combined with percussion and low staccato strings, horns are essentially used for melodies and counter melodies. Furthermore, ostinato which is a short melodic or rhythmic repeating pattern became a primarily used technique in his string-based compositions to evoke tension or a pulse of a heartbeat (Baxmusic).

We can see this happening in “Chevaliers de Sangreal”, where there is a tripled-based ostinato played by violins forming the basis of the piece. It is primarily composed of the notes D, F, and A found in a D minor chord. Specifically, Zimmer consistently goes back to the D root note after every other note, which serves as an anchor. He ends the 1st bar with a Bb, which is the 6th degree of a D minor scale (Fig 3.1, circled in red), to give it some variation. On the second bar, it is played again but with a high D instead of the Bb, as we can see in Fig 1 circled in red (Composing Academy). Furthermore, Hans Zimmer often combines electronic components, current technology, and traditional orchestral instruments to produce

a distinctive sound. He blends the flexibility and synthetic textures of electronic instruments with the depth of an acoustic ensemble creating a hybrid orchestration.

Figure 1. “Chevalier De Sangreal” Opening Ostinato

John Williams

The music of John Williams’ Star Wars film and Ludwig Gorransson’s The Mandalorian share a common universe and musical heritage, but they also show distinct developments of film scores. John Williams has played a major role in the Skywalker Saga over 9 films and more than 40 years, bringing dozens of iconic themes: “For Yoda”, “Imperial March” and “Darth Wader” to life throughout the galaxy in a beautiful neoclassical manner. According to Gorranson, “What John Williams created for Star Wars was probably the best film music out there at least, the most known film music. I remember watching the movies as a kid and the impact the visuals and the music had on me,” he says. “I can still remember that feeling, and it was that feeling that I wanted to try to recreate.”(Greiwings, 2020).

Massive orchestras have always been used in Star Wars music. For his compositions, John Williams requires the London Symphony Orchestra to perform at full capacity. Ludwig Gorranson recorded The Mandlorian’s score with a 70-piece orchestra in the first season and a 40-piece string orchestra with added digital changes in the second season.

He kept Williams’ traditions with a new auditory dimension in The Mandalorian. This method produces a new sound that captures The Mandalorian’s distinct tone and setting, which is different from the original Star Wars sage but yet has a connection to its core (Sherlock, 2021).

John Williams, not only demonstrates his proficiency with harmonic devices but also with captivating rhythmic strategies that elevate the music. The flow of a composition can be significantly affected by changing the time signature. Although altering the time signature is a straightforward process, the difficulty is in preserving a melodic shift without interfering with the composition’s general flow. As goes for Hans Zimmer, Williams uses ostinato that plays continuously throughout a song. This pulse rarely, if ever, stops completely during a composition. One instrument gives away to another and together they carry the rhythmic pattern. I encountered this, in the Beach Boys’Pet sounds. Williams has used the same compositional technique for all 3 of his film scores for Star Wars, Jurassic Park, and Superman: the tonic-dominant interval, which is a change in pitch from the scale’s first note to its fifth, in other words, an I-V or perfect fifth interval (ClassicFM). Since the I-V connection is one of the basic melodic relationships in Western Harmony, using it in composition is nothing new. However, a lot of John Williams’s well-known tunes are built around this interval. He uses the I-V interval as a tool for moving us straight into the catchy bit of the song rather than merely using it as a component of the melody. The most well-known piece of music to ever be included in a movie is the Star Wars theme.

Figure 2. First 6 Measures of the Star Wars Main Theme

As we can see in Fig 2, in measure 2 (highlighted in pink), two half notes G and D create the I-V, followed by the triplet motif. This occurrence happens again in measure 6. Williams uses this as a launching point for the remaining part of the phrase and the entire piece. The suspension trick is the most infamous effect that instantly leads to John Williams.

Figure 3. Measure 29-31, Star Wars Main Theme

For example, in Star Wars, we can hear it when the camera cuts from a fixed starry sky to the opening scene, and to create suspense and tension, it usually comes after fast-paced music. Typically, the woodwinds usually create this “Suspension Trick” effect because of their unique timbre, which allows them to be both gentle and menacing. It uses spurious notes in addition to two superimposed major triads. The second major triad is placed in the middle along with the extra note, while the first triad has very spread voicing (Expert, 2022). In Fig.3, the piccolo, oboe, and bassoon comprise the initial triad, which is in F major. The clarinet and bass clarinet perform the second triad, which is in A major. The oboe completes the triad by sharing a note with the previous one. And the flute produces a false D sharp.

Figure 4. Measures 14-15. Minor Triads Using Multi-Harmonious Movements in Half-Steps

Figure 5. Measure 14-15. A Low Brass Pedal Used to Produce Multi-Harmonious Trumpet Calls

Using a similar methodology, the second half features piccolo playing a spurious A, the bass clarinet, clarinet, and oboe playing an E flat major, and flute, oboe, and bassoon playing a wide C flat major. Another technique that creates tension that appears in practically every one of Williams’s works is the half-step movements made by minor triads (Expert, 2022). In Fig 4, The upper woodwinds are playing descending triads from A flat minor to D flat minor, as well as F minor, G flat minor, and F minor. The constant switching of chords makes it impossible to pinpoint a single harmonic structure, emphasized by the staccato trumpet calls in A minor, which are accompanied by low brass and woodwinds playing an F pedal (see Fig 5).

Ennio Morricone

Ennio Morricone was a composer, who skillfully combined extremes, blending extreme and delicate beauty to produce a great body of work spanning over 500 films and 6 decades (BBC). The first compositional technique is a riff or rhythmic ostinato that Hans Zimmer and John Williams employ. This pulse rarely, if ever, stops completely during the composition where one instrument gives way to another, creating a rhythmic train. Another technique is the use of the human voice as a melodic instrument, encompassing calls, whistles, and whoops and hollers heard in the music of certain “Spaghetti” Westerns . Morricone frequently used non-musical elements and a variety of sound effects in addition to traditional instruments, He made effective use of these sounds to improve the compositions, rhythmic and atmospheric elements like nature sounds, fire crackling, gunfire, etc (Dimura, 2018) . They were all incorporated into the music to increase its realism and immersion. To see all of these techniques, we will look into “The Ecstasy of Gold” (see appendix) from “The Good, the Bad, and the Ugly”. The main 2 note leitmotif of the score, which mimics the howl of a coyote is introduced by a steady 2 whole notes, 2 quaver drumbeat. This motif, which appears throughout the movies, is played on a variety of instruments, usually, a call-and-response sequence is used. Afterward, following a brief drum march, the theme begins with four notes that descend on what is best described as “wa-wa’s” and 5 notes on high-pitched woodwinds.

Figure 6. Measure 1-4 in the Opening of “Ecstasy of Gold”

Furthermore, it starts with an arpeggiated piano melody which is composed with just 4 notes over 2 chords as seen in Fig 6. Root A and the fifth, E over the Am9. The melody line, which has the third, B, and the root, G, comes after the arpeggiated piano part below changes to a G9. The notes used over G9, the root and the third, are part of the parent chord Am(7)9 and serve as the dominant seventh and ninth, respectively. As a result, even though the underlying harmony is changing, the melody continues the previous chord, A strong line that develops without changing past the uncomfortable point is produced by this relationship and its harmonic efficiency. Morricone understood the value of silence. He implemented quiet passages to his compositions like “The Hateful Eight”, to heighten the suspense and anxiety of the intense scenes.

Ludwig Göransson

One of the best TV scores of our time is quickly being recognized as being the soundtrack for *The Mandalorian*. Ludwig Göransson, a Swedish composer, conductor, and record producer, is widely recognized for his varied musical styles and creative approaches to film scoring. He received an Emmy for Outstanding Music Composition for a Series and an OFTA (Online Film & Television Association) award for his work on the show (Testerman, 2021).

The music for *The Mandalorian*, which draws inspiration from the compositions of John Williams, Hans Zimmer, and Ennio Morricone, perfectly captures the spirit of the space western genre.

While writing *The Mandalorian*, Göransson thought about John Williams's state of mind when the *Star Wars* scores were being written in the 1970s. He immersed himself in the soundtracks of pre-*Star Wars* films to better understand this. He expressed particular interest in the creative use of synthesized orchestras and drums and noted a particular enthusiasm for the "Earthquake" soundtrack. Through this, he was able to recognize Williams' take on developing his themes (“Ludwig Göransson drew inspiration for 'The Mandalorian' from pre-*Star Wars* John Williams scores”, 0:00-1:54).

Göransson plays all guitar parts, recorders, piano, bass, and rock drums in *The Mandalorian*. He uses the Mellotron and the Fender Rhodes, 2 classic rock instruments from the 1970s. Göransson says “John Williams uses celeste a lot; glockenspiel and celeste are flavors he uses to convey a nostalgic or storybook feeling. I love using the Rhodes for that because it sounds nostalgic, like bells.” The Mellotron is a vintage 1960s keyboard that was popularized by bands such as The Beatles and The Moody Blues. It enhances the authenticity of the score by adding depth through the use of tape loops that contain real orchestral instruments (Greiving, 2020).

The opening motif of *The Mandalorian* is only played on a bass recorder, which is an embodiment of past musical traditions. The connection with an old sound is strengthened by the fact that wind instruments, like the bass recorder, are among the earliest known musical instruments. Wind instruments are associated with a more simple musical quality, a connection that affects our understanding of music and often occurs subconsciously. Another aspect of this recorder part is its pitch

Figure 7. First 2 Measures of the Main Theme of “The Mandalorian” Played by a Recorder

During the intro (see Fig. 7), when listening to the score, the notes that the recorder is hitting aren't perfectly in tune. They fluctuate quite a bit. The sound produced by this instrument, which oscillates between G and D in perfect fifths which is easily recognizable as John Williams’ technique, strengthening the bond with the Star Wars franchise. Furthermore, This selection is reminiscent of the melodic themes in Ennio Morricone’s score for “The Good, the Bad, and the Ugly”. Morricone is renowned for his unique use of straightforward yet powerful intervals in his music. This rhythmic motif draws listeners into the story and adds to the organic feel of the score.

Figure 8. Showing 3 flats (B, E, A) = C minor

The overall key of the *Mandalorian* is C minor, even though the introduction begins in G minor

Figure 9. Measures 3 and 4 of the Main Theme of “The Mandalorian”, Played by a Recorder

The melody changes into a minor 7th interval, going from G to F, as the piece moves into measures 3 and 4.

Figure 10. Measures 5-8 of the Main Theme of “The Mandalorian”, Played by a Recorder

The music shifts to a minor third interval, G- Bb, in measures 5 and 6. The melody then changes to a minor fourth, from G to C, in measure 6 to 8. These transitions show a journey through tension and release, a common feature of Western music, which often uses dissonance and consonance to evoke strong feelings.

Figure 11. Measure 16-18 of the Main Theme of “The Mandalorian”, Showing a Guitar and Percussion Ostinato

Beginning at measure 17 (Fig 11), the bass guitar part introduces a distinctive ostinato, reflecting 3 composers (Hans Zimmer, John Williams, Ennio Morricone), and plays a crucial role in shaping the score’s character. This rhythmic motif of the guitar in addition to the percussion evokes the sound of a galloping horse, creating a clear connection to the spaghetti western genre that Ennio Morricone is credited with popularizing through his compositions.

Figure 12. Measures 25 and 26 of the Main Theme of “The Mandalorian”

The bassline (highlighted in pink) and guitar (highlighted in blue) in Fig 12 engage in a dialogue-like fashion in measures 25 and 26, almost producing a call-and-response effect. This dynamic exchange is reminiscent of Williams’ frequent use of thematic dialogue between instruments and Ennio Morricone’s illustration of the vast distances between people in a prairie or speaking across an intercom in space.

Figure 13. Measure 27-30 of the Main Theme of “The Mandalorian”

In measure 30 (Fig 13 red brackets), there is a Neapolitan chord which is a major chord constructed on the flattened second scale degree. In particular, Goransson substitutes a major triad of Db/F for the expected IV chord in C minor. This added an unexpected harmonic color which transitions us into the next part of the song. John Williams and Ennio Morricone rarely employ this specific harmonic move. Goransson's use of the Neapolitan chord here adds an unexpected level of sophistication and emotional complexity and sets him apart from these composers.

Figure 14. Measure 25-26 of the Main Theme of “The Mandalorian”

Figure 15. Notated G Diminished Half Whole Scale. G Ab Bb B C# D E F

In measure 25 (Fig 14), Goransson uses a half-whole diminished scale beginning at G with the notes G Ab Bb B C# D E F (Fig 15). A sequence of alternating semitones and tones in this scale evoke tension and uneasiness. This scale's application enhances the score's dramatic landscape and is consistent with the themes of conflict and resolution found in both space Western and Western genres.

Conclusion

This study has brought to light the compositional strategies used by Ludwig Goransson in “The Mandalorian”, highlighting influences of composers like John Williams, Hans Zimmer, and Ennio Morricone in terms of compositional techniques and thematic motifs. Significant findings like Goransson’s inventive use of instrumentation, such as the opening motif of the bass recorder, refer to monophonic textures and old-fashioned musical traditions. Perfect fifths and minor intervals are used in a way that is reminiscent of Morricone’s approach and the ostinato patterns and rhythmic motifs are typical of the spaghetti western genre. Williams’ influence is further demonstrated by the addition of a Neapolitan chord, which offers unexpected harmonic color. The score’s dramatic tension is further amplified by the half-whole diminished scale, which is consistent with the themes of conflict and resolution found in both space Western and traditional Western genres.

This analysis was done through a thorough examination of Goransson’s score as well as the compositions of significant composers. Through a closer look at particular measures and methods, I was able to understand how Goransson combines contemporary aspects with traditional ones. My comprehension of the complex relationship between modern scoring and historical influences was strengthened by my engagement with both primary and secondary sources, including the official score and interviews.

When examining how much The Mandalorian score paid tribute to Williams, Zimmer, and Morricone, Goransson not only preserves their legacy but also pushes the boundaries by incorporating novel elements. His use of traditional instrumentation and thematic development creates a distinct soundscape that is appealing to Mandalorian’s fans while still having ties to the legendary score that came before it. The limitation of this research is that the scope of Goransson’s score may not be fully covered due to its concentration solely on “The Mandalorian” theme. Further studies might broaden the scope of the analysis to look at the entire show’s score and investigate how themes change from episode to episode. Furthermore, investigating the relationship between musical composition and visual storytelling could deepen our knowledge of how scores improve narrative engagement in contemporary media.

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